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FYDP Project Report

Development of Smart Parking and
Charging Station for Electric Bike

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Abstract

It has been observed that petrol and diesel consumption in many countries have increased remarkably. With the enhancement in the fuel price over the past few decades the whole world is moving towards eco-friendly renewable energy resources, the idea of the electric bicycle is also eco-friendly and is used for transportation purposes. To solve the problem, we design and implement an intelligent parking system. The whole project will be designed in such a way that the rider can choose his/her mode of cycling. We will design our project in such a way that people of any age can be used it without any difficulty. Our idea of implementation of the project is mainly biased towards providing an enter-public transportation system with parking and reducing the use of automobiles inside the cities, universities, large area industries, and Headquarters as a tribute to the "GREEN ENERGY". Finally, we give a deployment instance of the system and discuss its possible applications.

Introduction

We make a smart parking system where we use RFID. A bicycle can be used by scanning a card. However, there are bi-cycle docking stations available in different countries but we aim to change them with Electric Bikes so that one can easily travel. We aim to charge these bikes with a free energy source (Solar Energy).

Our idea for the implementation of the project is based on the development of a smart and secure docking station with the main feature of Electrical Vehicle charging. It can be used in public places in the cities, educational institutes, industries, organizations, etc. Our idea is to facilitate the people with a smart and secure parking system in Pakistan as a tribute to the “GREEN ENERGY”.

In this project, smart and secure docking stations for two-wheelers are developed with the feature of charging from the solar panel for Electric Vehicles. The user will scan his identification card and the vehicle will be unlocked after verification from the database. A smart mechanical system is developed to lock or unlock the vehicle.

Project Background

Docking stations are one of the successful green transport in well-developed countries which should be implemented in our country. Moreover, in implemented docking stations, the rider's energy is required to derive the pedals of the bicycle. But we aimed to make it user-friendly transport so we decided to advance it by using the benefit of Electrical Machines as it is a method to derive a bike without any exhaust. So it is an environment-friendly mode of travel. The Implementation of bicycles has been done by an FYP group of Batch-2017. Now we have to develop the Charging Station and design a Lock/Unlock mechanism by using an RFID System.

Objectives

The main outcomes/objective of this proposed project are as follows.

- Development of a cost-effective smart docking system.
- Development of efficient solar charging stations for electric vehicles.
- Development of the simulation model in the PROTEUS environment.
- Development of hardware and its implantation in real-time at a laboratory scale.
- Testing the designed solution at a laboratory scale.
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Project Implementation Method

The implementation of the proposed project will be in the five steps

At first, the solar charging station for simulation modeling has been developed and performed on **PROTEUS/Simulink software**.

We set the input voltage to 12-24V. This will be regulated and supplied to the output.

Voltage less than 12 volts will be boosted to give supply, this maintains continuity even if the voltage drops. The attached LCD module shows the values of voltage and current.

Docking station hardware design on AutoCAD

Figure 1(Frame designing)

Rack and Gear Design (AutoCAD)

With the rack and pinion mechanism, the rotation of the pinion causes linear motion of the rack. Rack and pinion systems are a common component in many mechanical applications. A rack and pinion system consists of a pinion (a circular gear) with a rack (a linear gear).

Second, Interfacing of components with Microcontroller and Motor automatic forward reverse control system.

The motor moves forward and reverse for lock and unlock for that purpose we designed a circuit for an automatic forward and reverse control system using relays.

Third, programmed the microcontroller to access data from a real-time database and perform the action.

Fourth, the Implementation of a lock/unlock the frame

The frame is designed in such a way that, with the movement of gear in rotatory motion the rack moves in linear motion and locks the system.

A fifth. The integration of our proposed project, after the testing and checking of the working of the project, we integrate our proposed project into one form.

Applications of the Project

- Smart User Identification.
- Secure Mechanical Docking System
- The renewable energy source is used for charging.
- The proposed project meets the eco-friendly and cost-effective system.